

Interrelation and correlation of international security, national security and constitutional security concepts

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In light of the tasks set in this article, it is appropriate to mention, that the primary social function of international law is to strengthen the existing international system, ensuring its proper functioning. This function is carried out largely by maintaining international law and order. The meaning of this provision is relevant and important. The 1996 Advisory Opinion of the International Court of Justice on Nuclear Weapons states that international law is designed to ensure stability of the international order. It should also be noted that at the heart of all human rights is the inalienable right to live in a secure world and this right, like many others, can only be ensured in conditions of a stable international legal order.

In order to more specifically define the theoretical concepts of "international security", "national security" and "constitutional security" considered in this article, as well as to determine their close relationship with each other, let us first of all turn to the category of security indivisibility. The concept of security indivisibility is based on the recognition that international security is the security of groups or even all states, and it is the indivisibility of security that makes it possible to assert the relationship and close interconnection of concepts mentioned above.

The study of security issues in the modern world, both at the national and international levels, is "an urgent need not only to preserve their geopolitical position of individual states, but also for people and all mankind survival" [1, p. 10].

International security is a state of international relations that excludes the violation of global peace or the creation of a threat to peoples, states, security of interstate associations in any form. Its main components are political, economic, military, environmental and other types of security. International security can be global (universal) or regional (European, Asia-Pacific, Middle East, etc.).

International security presupposes the construction of a system of international relations based on the observance of universally recognized principles and international law norms, excluding the settlement of disputed issues and disagreements by way of force or the threat of its use.

The functions of state systems for ensuring national security contribute to ensuring international security in general. Conversely, the international security mechanism also depends on the level of national security. Humanity has entered the 21st century, which is characterized by the growing process of globalization. As a result, each person is interconnected to others in a variety of relationships. A united world community is being formed, where not only the well-being of individuals is at stake, but also the survival of mankind, which can only be ensured only by the joint efforts of states and people.

Today, the security and well-being of each country depends on the state of the international system of relations between states [2, p. 2].

National security of international law subjects is a global problem of the entire world community. The more a state is involved in the system of international relations, the more it grows dependent on the international community, the more open its legal system becomes to direct action of international law, and the more likely that this state recognizes the priority of international law. Article 8 of the Constitution reads: "The Republic of Kazakhstan respects the principles and norms of international law, pursues a policy of cooperation and good-neighborly relations between states, their equality and non-interference in each other's internal affairs, peaceful resolution of international disputes, and refuses to use the first armed force."

The development of the international legal foundations of national security is objectively influenced by two tendencies in the states' position: the desire for mutual cooperation and natural concern for the protection of their own sovereignty and independence from external threats. In this regard, in the international legal order, there are also tendencies for the development and consolidation at the international legal level of a model of a new order that meets all states' interests, and in essence the interests of their national security. In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated January 6, 2012 "On the National Security of the Republic of Kazakhstan", the national security of the Republic of Kazakhstan is defined as the state of protection of the national interests of the Republic of Kazakhstan from real and potential threats, ensuring the dynamic development of a person and citizen, society and the state.

And, finally, constitutional security, which is largely determined by the development of political and civil society institutions, the development of the state's economy, a constant increase in material well-being, and the socio-cultural component of society and the state (spiritual, historical, legal education, cultural traditions, and national characteristics and values). The basis for constitutional security is primarily high-quality constitutional legislation and its effective implementation. Constitutional security ensures the implementation of the Constitution of Kazakhstan; it is aimed at the stability of the constitutional system of the Republic of Kazakhstan and serves as the backbone of national security.

Constitutional security is understood as "the internal security of the state, which presupposes the state of protection of the foundations of the country's constitutional system from threats that are predominantly internal in nature, and at the same time ensures the stable, progressive development of the individual, society and the state" [3, p. 2].

Constitutional security is a constitutional protection system; a system of regulatory, organizational, and institutional guarantees that ensures its protection. It is important to note here that the degree of social stability in a state is important in maintaining security. Therefore, obstacles in constitutional legal relations subject's activities stimulate social tension and enhance the social activity of the subjects and, accordingly, generate conflict situations. Dissatisfaction with needs, mismatch of interests and goals of the subjects of constitutional and legal interaction is the main social tension source. The prevention of conflicts existing in society, including constitutional and legal ones, will remove social tension and thus remove threats to constitutional security, since the resolution of conflicts means reaching a public consensus, taking into account all public interests.

A prerequisite for the recognition of a conflict as constitutional and legal is the presence in its subject matter of a controversial legal fact of a constitutional and legal nature and the possibility of ending the confrontation between the parties using constitutional and legal procedures. Constitutional security implies the protection of basic values, constitutional institutions, and the constitutional order itself, enshrined in the Constitution. This requires a scientific understanding of the mechanisms for ensuring constitutional security in a constantly changing political and legal environment, which is based on the interests and needs of the subjects

of constitutional legal relations, aimed at basic constitutional values, determining the ability of the country's legal system in a specific historical period to ensure the protection of the interests of the subjects of law: the individual, public institutions, and the state.

The specificity of constitutional conflicts is associated with the particular composition of the participants, namely the people, government bodies and political parties. International law cannot directly regulate domestic relations, for example, issues relating to the legal status of persons who make up the population of states. The regulation of the legal status of individuals located in the territory of a state and constituting its population is within the exclusive purview of each state. As for the objects about which a constitutional conflict may arise, it is necessary to note the specifics of sovereignty and territory. And these are inalienable signs of any state - a subject of international law. Therefore, constitutional security is generally a means of ensuring both national and international security.

Ensuring constitutional security within countries is especially important in view of the fact that constitutional conflicts undermine the foundations of international security, first at the regional and then at global levels, since in the conditions of good-neighborliness, hotbeds of tension and conflicts affect good-neighborly relations and the stability of relations existing in neighboring countries.

References:

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